

**THE PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ENGLISH WITH NEW METHODS FOR
THE FIRST YEAR STUDENTS**

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Annotation: The classroom teacher and the program coordinator have a wider variety of methodological options to choose from than ever before. They can choose methods and materials according to the needs of learners, the preferences of teachers, and the constraints of the school or educational setting.

Key words: Students, foreign, communicative, teachers, example, pronunciation, folktales

Students will have to speak English everywhere in order to communicate: in the store, in supermarkets, in the street, in the classroom, in dining halls and in restaurants. Many foreign students attend ESL classes before getting academic courses. If we'll look at the numbers, students represent the majority of foreign students. There are more than three hundred students at the university every year. Since English classes for foreign students consist of 15-18 students, there are usually about students in each group. The same problem exists with students. The schedule of the classes is prepared beforehand, so that students can choose the suitable time and teacher for them. Students usually try to get in the same group with their friends. It creates one of the main problems. When there are more than three or four representatives of one nation in a group, those students usually speak native language with each other during the English classes as well. Usually students do less progress than the representatives of other countries.

This is because they keep speaking in native, English language. It also influences their achievements during the classes. The problems which may occur with communicative language teaching in Uzbekistan is are as follows. Let us bring examples to the statements brought above. As it is written above, in the form of social interaction

activities of communicative language teaching are included debates, discussions, dialogues and role plays, skits and others which help to increase the social skills of the students. In this point of view teachers pay attention to the opinion of the student, what the student want to say. Usually teachers don't interrupt the student's speech to correct grammatical mistakes that they have done. Because if they do so they might create the thought in the student's mind that they should speak only in a case when they are sure not to make any grammatical mistake. Or sometimes students might easily get ashamed. Planning to tell it after the students' speech unintentionally teachers forget the fifty percent of the errors that they would like to tell. As well in Uzbekistan University in English classes for foreign students' discussions and debates are used a lot in order to develop speaking skills of the foreign students. The students have to do class presentation about their own culture. It may be about proverbs, games, folktales, forms of address, standards of conduct, ceremonies, and holidays of their countries. The teacher never interrupts any student while talking. Neither have they corrected pronunciation mistakes, nor grammatical ones. As a result of which for some students it became more difficult to produce sentences accurately, to use the grammar correctly, to have the right pronunciation of the words. Teacher usually corrects mistakes after the students' speech. Let us bring another example on functional communication activities of the communicative language teaching method.

The teacher has the students divide into groups of three. Since there are 15 students, there are five groups of three students. One member of each group is given a picture strip story. There are six pictures in a row on a piece of paper, but no words. The pictures tell a story. The student with the story shows the first picture to the other members of his group, while covering the remaining five pictures. The other students try to predict what they think will happen in the second picture. The first student tells them whether they are correct or not. He then shows them the second picture and asks them to predict what the third picture will look like. After the entire series of pictures has been shown, the group get a new strip story and they change the roles, giving the first student an opportunity to work with a partner in making predictions. Students use new vocabulary words orally. In many cases they do mistakes while writing words of foreign origin and

long words as well. Teachers divide students into the groups paying attention to their learning potential. They try to mix the students with different levels, so that there will not be a group of only passive students or a group of only active students. Teachers make sure that there are students with different levels: passive, active and normal. Teacher divides fifteen students into three groups of five.

Gives the theme to each group and asks them to make a presentation on their themes. Teacher gives the students thirty minutes. Active students in the group immediately begin discussing what they will do, until passive students just begin taking a pencil as if they are going to write some ideas. Passive students can't get involved into the group as much as the actives do. As a result of which two or three active students do the main part of group's work. Passive students remain to be passive. This situation happens a lot in informal group working. Every student does the test on his own. Their scores depend on their results as a group. This rule sometimes may discourage the students who have done well. They may think that it is not fair to be punished for others fault who has done worse at the tests. It also changes the attitude of students who have done well towards the rest of the group. Let us take another example. Foreign students usually are taught grammatical theme first then are given text to find the means of the exact grammar that is passed by the teacher. Teacher explains the grammatical theme properly. This is a usual procedure in home countries of foreign student.

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